

Assessment of River Thermal Energy Potential in Baden-Württemberg, Germany

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1 Background

Rivers, as continuously flowing water bodies with relatively stable temperatures, represent a promising source of renewable thermal energy and provide a climate-friendly option for supporting heating systems. Thermal energy stored in flowing river water can be extracted using water-source heat pump technologies and utilized for space heating and district heating applications. In addition to established renewable heat sources such as geothermal energy and ambient air heat pumps, rivers offer a largely underutilized and spatially extensive thermal resource. To facilitate the integration of river-based heat sources into municipal heat planning, it is necessary to estimate the available thermal potential at a sufficiently refined spatial resolution. Assessments conducted at refined river reaches enable a more detail evaluation of locally available resources and help identify suitable locations for potential heat extraction systems. The thermal energy available in a river is primarily determined by its discharge and the allowable temperature reduction associated with heat extraction.

The present analysis focuses on estimating the theoretical thermal potential of rivers within the German federal state of Baden-Württemberg. Using long-term, spatially refined hydrological simulations, this report provides a first-order assessment of river thermal energy potential across multiple river reaches in the study region. Thermal potentials are estimated for different temperature extraction scenarios, and the resulting distributions are summarized using characteristic curves that describe the variability and magnitude of thermal energy potential across the river network.

2 Methodological Framework

River discharge data used in this study are derived from simulations produced by the mesoscale Hydrologic Model (mHM; Samaniego et al. [2010], Kumar et al. [2013]). The mHM is a spatially explicit hydrological model designed for regional to continental scale applications (see <https://mhm-ufz.org> for details). The model has been extensively calibrated and evaluated across German river basins and has been applied in numerous hydrological and water resource studies, including the online German Drought Monitoring system (Zink et al. [2016], Boeing et al. [2022]; <https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=37937>). The model provides continuous simulations of hydrological variables at high spatial resolution and is capable of estimating river discharge at approximately 1 km river reach resolution.

For the present study, simulated river discharge data were obtained at a daily temporal resolution for the 40 year period starting at 1971. The long-term dataset allows the derivation of robust flow statistics representing typical, low-flow, and high-flow conditions. The hydrological simulations were driven by the daily gridded forcings of precipitation, air temperature, and po-

tential evapotranspiration which constitute the primary meteorological inputs to mHM. Details on the model specifications including model parameterizations and other required input data are presented in Boeing et al. [2022].

Not all river reaches are suitable for thermal energy extraction. Rivers with very low discharge may not provide sufficient carrying capacity to reliably support continuous heat extraction. In addition, excessive heat extraction under low-flow conditions may increase the risk of crossing ecological flow, among other temperature constraints. Therefore, river reaches were first screened based on their long-term mean minimum annual discharge (MNQ). Only reaches with $MNQ \geq 0.5 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ – corresponding to 500 L/s [Leßmann and Riedmüller, 2025] – were selected for further analysis of the potential assessment.

Because river heat extraction is primarily relevant for space heating, the analysis focuses on the winter season when heating demand is high. Herein, the winter season is defined as the period from October through April. For each selected river reach, daily discharge values during the winter months were extracted from the full 40 years simulation period. From this simulation database, empirical flow distributions were constructed and summarized using different flow quantiles for a statistical representation of the hydrological variability during the winter season. To this end, the following quantiles were calculated for each river reach:

- Q_1 – near-minimum winter daily flow
- Q_{10} – representative low-flow condition
- Q_{25} – lower quartile flow
- Q_{50} – median winter daily flow
- Q_{75} – upper quartile flow
- Q_{90} – representative high-flow condition
- Q_{99} – near-maximum winter daily flow

The theoretical thermal energy potential (E_p) that can be extracted from a given river reach at a defined flow condition (Q_x), assuming an allowable temperature reduction (ΔT), can be estimated using the following relationship:

$$E_p = \rho c_p Q_x \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where

- E_p is the thermal power potential (W),
- ρ is the density of water (1000 kg/m³),
- c_p is the specific heat capacity of water (4186 J/(kg K)),
- Q_x is river discharge (m³/s),
- ΔT is the allowable temperature reduction (K).

For each river reach and each discharge quantile, the thermal potential (E_p) was calculated for several temperature extraction scenarios ranging from $\Delta T = 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ to 3°C . Here, we present results using $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$ and 2°C , taking plausible extraction systems as illustration cases.

After calculating the thermal potential for each river reach, results were aggregated to obtain a regional overview of the available resources. To summarize the distribution of thermal potential across all river reaches in Baden-Württemberg ($N \approx 2160$), cumulative distribution functions

(CDFs) were constructed. These curves represent the fraction of river reaches that exceed a given potential thermal power threshold. CDFs was generated for each temperature extraction scenario and for each flow quantile. This allowed us to introspect the full spectrum of how river thermal potential varies across hydrological conditions and extraction scenarios.

3 Analysis Results

The analysis demonstrates that a large number of river reaches in Baden-Württemberg possess adequate discharge to support an extent of thermal energy extraction. However, the available potential varies regionally and substantially depending on hydrological conditions and the assumed temperature reduction. Figure 1 illustrates the spatial distribution of theoretical thermal power potential across river reaches in Baden-Württemberg for different flow conditions and temperature extraction scenarios. The maps present results for three representative winter flow quantiles (Q_{10} , Q_{50} , and Q_{90}) and two allowable temperature reductions ($\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$ and 2°C). Complementing this spatial map, the cumulative distribution functions shown in Figure 2 summarize the distribution of theoretical river thermal power potential across the selected river reaches in Baden-Württemberg for different winter flow conditions.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of theoretical river thermal power potential for all selected river reaches across Baden-Württemberg for winter flow quantiles (Q_{10} , Q_{50} , and Q_{90}) and allowable temperature reductions ($\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$ and 2°C). Thermal potential (E_p , MW) is estimated for river reaches with $MNQ \geq 0.5 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ (see text for details).

Overall, the spatial distribution of thermal potential closely follows the structure of the regional river network and is strongly controlled by river discharge. Major rivers such as the Rhine, Neckar and Upper Danube exhibit the highest thermal energy potentials due to their

Figure 2: Cumulative distribution functions (CDF) of theoretical river thermal power potential across all selected river reaches in Baden-Württemberg for different winter flow quantiles. The curves represent flow percentiles ranging from low-flow to high-flow conditions (Q_1 – Q_{99}). Panel (a) shows results for an allowable temperature extraction of $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$, while panel (b) shows results for $\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$.

substantially larger flow volumes. Their respective river reaches show thermal power potentials reaching several thousand megawatts under high-flow conditions (Q_{90}) and with a temperature extraction levels ($\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$) nearly 20,000 MW. In contrast, smaller tributaries distributed throughout the interior of Baden-Württemberg display comparatively lower potentials, typically in the range of a few megawatts to several tens of megawatts. The influence of hydrological variability is evident when comparing the different flow quantiles. Under low-flow conditions represented by the Q_{10} quantile, thermal potentials are significantly reduced across most river reaches (at $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$, values ranging between nearly 3 MW and 1700 MW). The median flow scenario (Q_{50}) represents typical winter conditions and reveals substantially higher potentials, ranging from nearly 7 MW to 4000 MW at the extraction level of $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$. Under high-flow conditions (Q_{90} or higher), thermal potentials increase further, particularly along large river systems (e.g., along the Rhine and the Neckar Rivers), with potential thermal heat of more than 5000 MW.

The cumulative distribution functions (CDF) shown in Figure 2 summarize the spatial distribution of thermal power potential across all river reaches. For example, at the median point of the distribution (CDF = 0.5), the estimated thermal potentials vary substantially across flow conditions. For the $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$ scenario, the median thermal potential for the Q_{10} flow percentile is approximately 10 MW, while the corresponding median value increases to roughly 40 MW for the Q_{50} flow percentile and to around 125 MW for the Q_{90} flow percentile. These differences reflect the strong dependence of thermal energy potential on river discharge conditions. When the allowable temperature extraction is increased to $\Delta T = 2^\circ\text{C}$, the estimated thermal potentials increase almost proportionally double across the entire distribution. Notably the contribution also varied along different CDF points, emphasizing the spatial differences due to small, medium and big river reaches.

Further, our analysis reveal distinct step-like increases in thermal potential at specific portions of the distribution (Figure 2). These jumps correspond to river reaches with substantially larger discharge, most likely associated with major river systems such as the Neckar and Rhine. The first pronounced increase occurs at approximately the 77th percentile of the CDF, which likely reflects the contribution of the Neckar and/or the Danube river system. At this point, for an allowable temperature reduction of $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$, the estimated thermal power potential in-

creases sharply across flow conditions. The corresponding thermal potentials are approximately 42 MW (Q_1), 78 MW (Q_5), 105 MW (Q_{10}), 174 MW (Q_{25}), 304 MW (Q_{50}), 518 MW (Q_{75}), 838 MW (Q_{90}), and about 1150 MW (Q_{95}). A second, even more pronounced increase appears around the 87th percentile of the CDF, which likely corresponds to reaches of the Rhine River, the largest river system within the study domain. For $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$, the estimated thermal power potential at this point rises to approximately 480 MW (Q_1), 720 MW (Q_5), 930 MW (Q_{10}), 1450 MW (Q_{25}), 2310 MW (Q_{50}), 3630 MW (Q_{75}), 5540 MW (Q_{90}), 7020 MW (Q_{95}), and up to about 10,450 MW (Q_{99}). These values highlight the substantial contribution of medium-to-large river systems to the overall thermal resource. A relatively sharp transitions in the CDF indicate that while a large fraction of river reaches contributes relatively modest thermal potentials, a smaller number of high-discharge rivers dominate the upper range of the theoretical thermal energy. This pattern is consistent with the spatial distribution of thermal potential observed in Figure 1, where the largest potentials are concentrated along the major river corridors.

Our analysis demonstrate that rivers in Baden-Württemberg represent a substantial source of renewable thermal energy with significant spatial variability across the river network. The estimated thermal potentials strongly depend on river discharge conditions, as reflected by the large differences between low-flow and high-flow quantiles. While many smaller tributaries provide modest thermal potentials, plausibly suitable for localized heating applications. Our report estimates the theoretical thermal energy potential of rivers, notably the actual utilization potential may be lower due to technical, environmental, and economic constraints. Factors such as heat pump efficiency, system losses, ecological limits on allowable temperature reductions, and the distance between river reaches and heat demand centers will influence the practical deployment of river-based heat extraction systems. While integrating these practical considerations, our analysis provides a first-order assessment drawing upon the characteristic of present-climate river thermal potential across the river systems of the Baden-Württemberg.

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